
Research Article

Improving the Quality of Foundation System of Traditional Dwelling in Rural Area
of Nigeria

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Abstract

The persistent foundation problems of the earth traditional building, collapse and dilapidation system and the plight of the affected majority in the past few years throughout the country has prompted an undertaking a foundation design verification survey of the earth building in the rural areas of the following states: Osun State, Ondo State, Sokoto State, Rivers State and Yobe State. The aim of which was to find out the main causes of the cracks and collapse affecting rural housing stock and National economy as a whole. The studies revealed that environmental degradation, shallow foundation construction practice, poor design and supervision, lack of maintenance, poor social economic situation and ignorance are the main causes of foundation problems. The total homelessness effect from annual earth building dilapidation has been enormous and from environmental considerations lots of expenses are wasted on the reinstatement of the collapse earth building. Bad construction practices were identified during the survey and their corresponding recommended procedures have also been indicated to help improve the situation.

Keywords: Earth, Traditional building, foundation failure, Requirement, Performance.

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Introduction

The foundation is structures which carry and distribute loads of any building structure known as sub-structure. Its main function is to ensure adequate strength and to provide structural stability to everything over it. Foundations are designed to ensure building stability against wind effect, also to distribute loads to the ground to prevent cracks and dilapidations.

The foundation structure basically consists of construction components, that strong enough to be able to carry super structure effectively. It has also been revealed that for the foundation material to function effectively, it should exhibits the following qualities, very durable, must have high resistance against, decay and deterioration also it must be effective against adverse weather conditions such as violent storm and wind pressure, seasonal temperature and moisture variation. In order to get effective and more reliable foundation structure, foundation should be of high quality and must function adequately as coherent system (Kneeland and Godfrey, 1986). It must be sufficiently strong and rigid enough to withstand any anticipated wind pressure, the design and construction must appropriate, effective and adequate. It should span the structural support without any form of deflection. Environmental factors and impact that affect the performance of foundation can be reduced through effective planned maintenance. Besides being one of the main structures in a building, foundation may act as an adequate support for the entire earth dwelling, therefore, it is important to treat any aging foundation promptly. In Nigeria, strip foundation which comprises of stone and sandcrete block has been adopted where it exist. Common defects include the decay and deterioration of construction component as a result of adverse weather effect. (Gaddy *et al.*, 1987).

Research Methodology

This paper concerns an investigation of the roof failure in traditional buildings in rural areas of Nigeria. A preliminary study involving the professionals in the construction industry identified problems and defects associated with the foundation of traditional building in rural area of Nigeria. The study used focus group to engaged rural dwellers in guided interview and discussion at the rural suburbs of Nigeria (Krueger, 1994). The participants are experienced local house developers from rural dwellers, the focus groups were led by research fellows, who are aided by a discussion guide developed through prior interview with, experts in building local houses and experienced in

building construction. The focus groups are a form quantitative researches in which purposely-selected participants in the field of study are interviewed in a group setting. Such setting increases the efficiency of interviewing and interaction among the group members, it leads to more insightful response than attained through individual interviews. Such a pattern suggests the probability of a generalized view within the population being studied. Focus group also carried out structural failure investigation of the foundation of traditional building, by collecting samples of specification used for construction by local builders to determine the relative structural fitness of those specifications.

Sample Frame

Since it is impossible to cover all the households in Nigeria due to cost and time, Six rural areas that cut across Northern, Southern, Eastern and Western part of Nigeria were studied. The Local Government Areas include: Ata-kumosa (Osun State), Akure south (Ondo State), Opobo Nkoro (Rivers State), Binji (Sokoto State) and Geshua (Yobe State).

Foundation Situation at the Rural Areas of Nigeria

Having carried out detailed studies in six states with the aid of effective professionalism in focus group, the prevailing foundation situations of traditional building in rural area are characterized with lack of good quality, poor construction management control measures, lack of maintenance, environmental degradation and lack of appropriate construction specifications. This resulted in several eartbuilding failures and total collapse. The performance evaluation of foundation system is very low due to incompetent builder and unacceptable low standard of workmanship, among others.

From the study, higher percentages of those building about seventy two percent have been existed for over thirty years without any maintenance measure administered over time. Majority of the rural housing stocks are characterized with partly collapsed, dilapidated and unsafe foundation situation that are dangerous for human habitation while those built in recent years constitute 18%, however there exists a correlation between relative habitation and age of the building. Fadamiro (1995) strengthens further that technical, functional and behavioral element of those building falls basically as traditional process, thus presenting an organic composition to maintenance and adaptability. These findings therefore emphasize the need for a comprehensive programme of effective rehabilitation for the improvement of technical, functional and behavioral performance of the existing rural indigenous dwelling.

Construction Materials and Methods

The Study Zones.

Un-stabilized earth that are far less than appropriate foundation specification form the commonest material upon which foundation constructions are based as ninety nine percent of all the buildings are constructed with inadequate material specification. However the use of those un-stabilized earth as a building material does not in itself build substandard and poor quality housing, but inability to strictly adhering to adequate specification with regard to constructional detail and constant routine maintenance (Chudley and Roger, 2006). Earth of different typology exhibits different characteristics that may or may not be suitable for foundation construction, the constructional processes that will enable high quality outcome depend apparently on the correct grade and composition of material used.

Performance Consideration of Foundation

Dupuis (1996) reported that the Performance or durability of foundation system is generally related to the fulfillment of the structural strength and stability, it means the actual functioning of a foundation system or element in service and the desired attributes of materials are the choice of builder. Obviously, these are considered the most important factors. Every foundation, irrespective of the material or the manufacturer, must be capable of doing the following:

- Remain waterproof.
- Withstand all weather factors (such as wind, rain, snow, hail, solar radiation, temperature extremes, and thermal shocks) during its intended service life.
- Resist various stresses from internal or external causes during manufacturing, application and service.

It may be appropriate to define some of the terms related to the performance of foundation system, materials or components in general.

- Performance requirement is a qualitative statement describing what the foundation system or element is to accomplish.
- Performance criterion is a quantitative aspect of the acceptable or adequate performance level.
- Characterisation method means a method for evaluating the compliance with performance criteria

It should be noted that requirement and criterion are interchangeable and to some it implies both, i.e, the qualitative aspect is implicit in the statement of the quantitative

aspects. The selection of a foundation typology, like any other building component, must be based on its ability to meet the performance requirements for proper functioning throughout its life.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The foundation system in terms of quality, effectiveness and performance in relation to rural housing, socio-economic characteristics and housing provision are analyzed as follows.

Table 1: Analysis of Factors Causing Foundation Failure

Predominant factors	Frequencies	
Effect of rainstorm	–	high
Effect of environmental degradation	low	–
Structural Inadequacy	–	high
Poor construction practice	–	high
Lack of maintenance culture	–	high
Poor economy factor	–	high

Field work (2018)

Table 2: Analysis of Construction Practice (Structural Characteristics)

Predominant factors	Practices frequencies	
Shallow foundation trenches	–	high
Construction material are sub-standard	low	–
Eccentric arrangement of super structure	–	high
Material are vulnerable to moist decay	–	high
Material unable to provide structural strength	–	high

Field work (2018)

Causes of Foundation Failure

A careful analysis from focused group revealed that main causes of foundation problem in the country include:

1) Effect of rainstorms disaster

The collapse and ripping off of earth building system during rainstorms especially in the rural areas is a common phenomenon in Nigeria. During these rainstorms disasters homeless and housing properties worth several millions of naira are always destroyed. The situation is worse in rural areas of Nigeria, where replacement of damage dwelling becomes always impossible due to their low incomes. Expensive building material in Nigeria have become difficult with ever increasing cost of reconstruct collapse building, these bring untold hardship to the affected people. It was revealed during this study that situation are worst off when delayed to replace these crack dwellings during the raining season which lead to total collapse of the earth wall structure. It has been proven also by the focus group that the total house can be left to be eroded and may not be replaced even in distant future, thereby reducing the national housing stock and worsening housing situation in Nigeria.

2) The effects of environmental degradation

The rural areas studied showed that sudden problem of frequent ripping off of collapse of building system can only be caused by destruction of the environmental forest. It has been revealed that most of old buildings, especially those in rural areas have been functioning for years, decades and beyond, without those problems, even though they are not properly designed or constructed. Thus clearing of forest and trees surrounding the building that is acting as wind breaks which protecting buildings from full impacts of the wind loads. Most of the buildings are now exposed to suffer full effect of the wind loads on the building with inadequate foundation system. The effect of environmental degradation was seen during the random survey in one village called Kajola in Ata-kumosa Local Government in Osun State where about fifteen houses had their roof blown off, with total collapse (Field work, 2018). In that particular case, the affected houses were opened up as a result of highway construction, all the trees around those buildings were possibly cleared with no natural wind breaks and were not replaced and were exposed to full impact of wind.

3) Structural Inadequacy

Structural problem was found to be one of major causes of collapse in some surveyed areas. It was discovered by focused group that foundation are basically designed using

approach which relies on experience and common sense. In such a situation, those artisans who possess these qualities are used to shallow trenches on soil strata that are not strong or firm enough to carry super structures those foundation are not resorting to design code and specification. Chudley and Roger (2006) corroborate further that there are some of the other practice that is very common among the less experienced artisan in under sizing up structural foundation component and composition, they always apply a total method of rule of thumb, which always resulted in very defective foundation system, which in most cases contribution to ripping off of building system. In the areas studied, especially at Npobo Nkoro it was also revealed that due to high cost of material, people always prefer un-stabilized earth which is relatively cheaper but structurally defective. The foundation structures constructed from these defective materials are not built to any design specification but left to the discretion of local artisans. The un-stabilize earth material without adequate particle size distribution makes the foundation system to be highly susceptible to damage caused by strong wind effect and decay caused by moisture. The principle of stabilization and compaction which provides good rigid structural system was completely ignored.

4) Poor construction practice

The report of focused group revealed that lack of adequate training of the artisans also contributed very greatly to the ripping off of building systems, due to poor construction methods. In some situations where the foundation components were structurally inadequate, due to poor construction, it becomes very defective and was easily blown off under serious wind storms. It was observed that either there was no anchorage of the roofing system to the rest of the building structure or the anchorage provided was not adequate. In some instances, purling were not firmly secured to the rafter, then purling ripped off together with the roof covering material especially zinc, leaving the rest of the roof structure behind (Chudley and Roger, 2006). Where the rafters are not firmly secured to the wall plates, the roofing system blew off leaving the wall plates behind. Wrong or inadequate fastener on the roof covering materials led to situation where roof covering materials blew off from the roof structure.

Also, majority of local foundation constructions were not compliance in design specifications and manufacturer requirements for the adequate foundation depth and material compositions, especially where the foundation have been constructed below construction code recommendation. These resulted in poor performances and are the major courses, these led to the deterioration of foundation structure and eventually fails. The survey of roof construction practices in the country revealed that there was a

complete lack of supervision during the construction by trained expert. The over reliance in the so called experience artisan is a major causes of the problems facing traditional building in rural areas, since the most construction by artisan are usually defective and can easily collapse.

5) Lack of maintenance culture

This study revealed that most of the building systems have undergone continuous deterioration. Also, after long time exposure to various environmental factors in the course of their services lives, it was realized that lack of effective maintenance of building systems in the rural areas, to combat the effect of time, hostile environment and repairs of defective area contributed to final collapse of buildings in the visited rural areas.

6). Poor economic factors, cost reduction and poor level of information required

During this study, it was discovered that poor economic situation, attempt to reduce the cost, non-standard construction material were used in most of the rural areas studied. Also out of their ignorance due to poor level of information about such construction material. Observations from the focused group revealed that artisans did not make use of basic principles of construction process to increase the stability and rigidity of the building system, even though material used were structurally inadequate and led to collapse of earth building system.

Performance Requirements

The performance of foundation as mentioned above, is related to numerous variables concerning weather factors and stresses. Other variables are the chemical composition of materials, the quality control of the constituent materials and products during manufacture, storage, transportation, installation and, maintenance. Most of these conditions vary from one situation to another, so that a large number of performance requirements and criteria are identifiable. In this paper, the foundation size, depth and material composition are discussed, e.g., the structural depth and wideness of foundation, have an important influence on the overall performance. One way to predict the performance of foundation is to identify the physical and mechanical properties essential for its performance and to quantify them arbitrarily on the basis of experience. These criteria may be projected with or without modifications to other generic types of foundation (Dupuis, 1996). Research and practical experience with the deterioration of foundation over a number of years have shown weather is one of the most potent factors that affects durability.

Conclusion

According to Addai, to ensure effective performance of any foundation system, the use of adequate material must comply with specification requirements. Also all construction component and materials must be partially or totally replaced after their service lives have passed, due to deterioration, also causes of leakages in roofs must be found and immediately remedied.

There is an urgent need to train artisans who are directly involved in the functional foundation realization especially those in the rural communities to at least know the basic construction techniques of a foundation system (Chudley and Rogers, 2006).

Recommendation

It is highly essential that specialist advice be sought in checking maintenance requirement of ensuring foundation of earth structure in the rural area, so that rate of deterioration can be reduced.

In the area of deforestation, where houses are exposed to full impact of windstorms tree planting programmes are highly recommended to serve as wind breaks. Also the rural artisans should be re-orientated that use of unseasonable material for construction must be regarded as bad practice and it should be avoided. Well characterized earthen material should be used at all time.

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